

System Identification of Hansa Aircraft using Physics-Informed Neural Networks with low-fidelity data

Ramkumar S., Dr. Devendra Ghate, Dr. Dhayalan R.

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1 Abstract

This paper presents a novel physics-informed neural network (PINN) architecture for aircraft system identification under low-fidelity data conditions. The aerodynamic model and parameters of the Hansa aircraft, obtained from the literature, were used as benchmarks for evaluation. The proposed architecture, named System-Identification PINNs (SI-PINNs) was first demonstrated to achieve estimation accuracy comparable to classical methods, including least squares, maximum likelihood estimation, and the Extended Kalman Filter, when applied to high-fidelity datasets. Subsequently, the architecture was evaluated through a set of four numerical experiments using synthetic data exhibiting various low-fidelity characteristics, including truncated data, time-offset measurements, multiple sampling frequencies, and data sparsity. The least squares method was employed as a baseline for comparison. The SI-PINN consistently outperforms the least squares method across all experiments involving low-fidelity data for a single state. This performance is achieved through a dual-network architecture comprising a dynamics network and a parameter network. The dynamics network constructs a surrogate representation of the state measurements using the available, potentially unstructured low-fidelity data, while the parameter network leverages physics-informed loss functions to estimate the aircraft parameters. This decomposition enables effective handling of truncated data, time-offset measurements, and varying sampling frequencies without the need for manual data preprocessing, thereby enhancing robustness to low-fidelity data. Furthermore, a generalized architecture, termed Robust SI-PINNs (RSI-PINNs), is introduced to handle low-fidelity data across all states. The proposed framework demonstrates superior performance over least squares estimation even under low-fidelity conditions for all states. These results highlight that the integration of physical knowledge with a modular network design enables accurate parameter estimation using lower-fidelity data acquisition systems, thereby offering potential resource savings.

2 Introduction

Machine learning is a branch of mathematics and artificial intelligence that uses data and algorithms to learn functions. The machine learning community has developed unique algorithms and methodologies for various classes of problems. As a result, it has found applications in many diverse fields such as computer vision, social media, object detection and recognition, natural language processing [11], [53], scientific and engineering disciplines, and in medicine[14].

Deep learning is a subset of machine learning methods based on artificial neural networks (ANN) with representation learning. Deep neural networks (DNNs) have been widely used in the science and engineering stream¹ and they have been successfully used to map a set of input to output parameters. This is also known as function approximation in the scientific community. This diverse and growing field is collectively known as scientific machine learning (SML).

In the field of aerospace engineering, ANNs were initially applied for mapping geometry parameters to aerodynamic coefficients[47], [59]. These were completely data-driven models which required generation of huge, expensive, and accurate experimental/computational datasets [6], [12], [20], [22]. Over the years, these applications have become more sophisticated with the increasing size of the network. Inverse problems in aerodynamic design[32], such as airfoil optimization[1], [4], [21], [54], have also been recently tackled using ANNs. Accurate data is difficult and expensive to generate in the scientific fields. As a

¹The theoretical justification for such an application comes from the universal approximation theorem for single layer feed forward network [9], and multi layer network [17].

result, learning was slow, and could yield non-physical predictions. Moreover, none of these techniques are capable of embedding prior knowledge of the underlying physics directly into the learning process.

Raissi, Perdikaris, and Karniadakis [39] proposed the first Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) to incorporate physics in the form of the residuals of the governing differential equations in the loss function. They illustrated the application of time-dependant continuous and discrete PINN models for solving the 1D viscous Burgers' equation in the spatio-temporal plane and also obtained good accuracy in shock capturing. Since then, there has been an explosion in the application of PINNs for fluid mechanics problems [27], [30], [51], [56]. Jin, Cai, Li, *et al.* [19] proposed the NSFnets to solve the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations for the ill-posed problems. Distributed learning machines (DLM) [10], conservative PINNs (cPINNs), Extended PINNs (XPINNs) [48] and fractional PINNs [35] have been introduced for the solution of fluid mechanics PDEs. A good review on various architectures of PINNs and their applications to fluid mechanics problems can be found in Cai, Mao, Wang, *et al.* [5].

For inverse problems, Yilmaz and German [57] have developed conditional GAN for airfoil inverse design. Raissi, Yazdani, and Karniadakis [40] have developed the Hidden Fluid Mechanics, which is a Navier-Stokes-informed deep learning framework for assimilating the quantitative data of fluid flow fields from the visualization data. Deep operator network (deep-o-net) [24], [25] is a model architecture developed based on the universal approximation theorem for operators [7]. Physics-informed deep-o-nets are capable of handling multi-fidelity data as well. [13], [18].

An interesting application of PINNs is the data-driven model discovery. Raissi, Perdikaris, and Karniadakis [39] used PINNs to compute the coefficients of viscous Burgers' equation and Navier-Stokes equations from the fluid flow field data. Model discovery using PINNs has also found applications in medicine. Grimm, Heinlein, Klawonn, *et al.* [14] have worked on PINN models that can estimate the contact rate and rate of contingency of a disease based on the data available from health science by imposing empirical governing equations as physics constraints to the networks. Malinzi, Gwebu, and Motsa [26] used PINNs for determining the COVID-19 dynamics. Recently, there were PINNs implementation in system identification from various fields [44], [50], [52]. This motivated us to explore the applications of PINNs to aircraft system identification.

System identification solves the difficult problem of modeling the system dynamics given the observations under minimal assumptions. In the most general case, nothing is known about the functional form of the differential equations governing the dynamics. An in-depth survey of deep learning methods for this general problem has been presented by Pilonetto, Aravkin, Gedon, *et al.* [38]. However, in case of aircraft, the differential form of the governing equations is known or can be guessed with good accuracy. This leads to a simpler problem of parameter estimation in which only the coefficients of the differential terms are to be determined. Parameter estimation is the experimental determination of values of unknown parameters in the governing equations of the system.

Aircraft parameter estimation assumes a suitable aerodynamic model, and the unknown aerodynamic coefficients in the model are estimated using flight data. Classical methods in aircraft parameter estimation are classified into: output error methods and equation error methods. Least-squares and maximum likelihood estimation are the popular output error methods, and the Kalman filter is based on the equation error method. Advantages of the classical parameter estimation techniques are speed, accuracy, and availability of theoretical error bounds. On the other hand, the present work shows that the classical methods require a relatively large amount of data and preprocessing for accurate parameter estimation.

Apart from the classical methods, the aircraft parameter estimation problem has also been tackled using data-driven machine learning techniques. Youssef and Juang [58] demonstrated the use of neural networks in estimating the aerodynamic coefficients in longitudinal flight simulation of F-16. Hess [16] has implemented the feed-forward neural networks with backpropagation algorithm for training the network for real-time aerodynamic estimation along with system fault detection and flight simulation. Raol and Jategaonkar [43] used Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) to estimate aerodynamic parameters and achieved the same accuracy as conventional output error methods. Peyada and Ghosh [37] used the neural Gauss-Newton method for the estimation of Hansa aircraft. The work was extended by Saderla, Dhayalan, and Ghosh [45] for estimating the aerodynamic parameters of a UAV. All of the above methods are data-intensive and do not embed the physics of the problem in the neural network architecture.

PINNs have also been applied for aircraft parameter estimation. Michek, Mehta, and Huebsch [29] demonstrated three PINN architectures for the aircraft parameter estimation: determinant PINNs, non-determinant PINNs and modified non-determinant PINNs. The authors have implemented the modified non-determinant PINNs for predicting the force coefficients of simulated 6 degrees of freedom F-16 model to show the potential of PINNs for aircraft parameter estimation. Application of PINNs has also been demonstrated for system identification of rotors in drones [23]. Gu, Primatesta, and Rizzo [15]

demonstrated successful application of PINNs for quadrotor system identification. Bianchi, Epicoco, Di Ferdinando, *et al.*[3] demonstrated the superiority of PINNs over extended Kalman Filters for on-line control. Peña-García, Velázquez-Sánchez, Gómez-Daza-Argumedo, *et al.*[36] investigated an hybrid approach of PINNs and Genetic algorithms for modeling the longitudinal dynamics of an aircraft.

In above works, the authors have discussed about the superiority of PINNs over classical estimation methods as well as the deep neural networks. The investigations are motivated by the robustness shown by deep learning methods for noisy data and ability of the networks to learn with smaller datasets. However, none of the studies present a systematic quantitative investigation of the superiority of the PINNs for handling low-fidelity datasets.

The present work demonstrates a successful application of PINNs in the system identification of Hansa aircraft[33]. We have built a new model architecture called System-Identification PINNs, (SI-PINNs) and demonstrated that it requires less data for the same accuracy and are robust to low fidelity datasets vis-a-vis classical methods.

Wind tunnel experiments on a 1/6 scale Hansa aircraft model was performed by Rangaranjan and Vishwanathan [42] and has provided a linear aerodynamic model, which is set as the benchmark reference for this work. As the variants of least squares are considered as the standard methods in aircraft system identification [34], we have used ordinary least squares, maximum likelihood estimation and Kalman filter based aerodynamic model estimation as the methods for comparison with SI-PINNs.

In the upcoming sections, we have presented the parameter estimation problem statement and an overview of PINNs. Descriptions of the Hansa aircraft model problem and its solution using SI-PINNs are presented in the further sections. We have also performed a set of numerical experiments with SI-PINNs to demonstrate its performance and capabilities against classical methods.

Subsequently, the SI-PINN framework was extended to enhance robustness against low-fidelity data across all state variables. The resulting architecture, named Robust SI-PINNs (RSI-PINNs), is presented in a separate section. Finally, the study is concluded by highlighting the advantages of the proposed (R)SI-PINNs architectures and outlining potential directions for future research.

3 Parameter estimation

In general, the dynamics of a physical system can be represented by a set of ODEs of the form

$$\mathbf{y} = \dot{\mathbf{x}} = f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\zeta}). \quad (1)$$

Here, $f(\cdot)$ is a sufficiently smooth nonlinear function of the state \mathbf{x} and the control \mathbf{u} . Further, $f(\cdot)$ is generally a nonlinear function of parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\zeta}$ that defines the system dynamics, for example the aerodynamic coefficients of an aircraft.

Solving the forward problem involves computing a time series of the \mathbf{x} vector with a defined \mathbf{u} vector and $\boldsymbol{\zeta}$ values. With the $\boldsymbol{\zeta}$ values provided, the forward problem generally leads to a system of coupled nonlinear equations. On the other hand, the inverse problem involves estimating the $\hat{\boldsymbol{\zeta}}$ values using the known time series data of the \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{u} vectors.

With a given set of experimental values of \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{u}_i , $i \in [1, N]$, computing the $\hat{\boldsymbol{\zeta}}$ is called the parameter estimation problem. Note, the control vector \mathbf{u} is selected in such a way that it has features to stimulate the near-complete dynamics of the system.

Further, for the inverse problem, if the parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\zeta}$ can be split into m sets, $\boldsymbol{\zeta} = [\boldsymbol{\zeta}_1, \boldsymbol{\zeta}_2, \dots, \boldsymbol{\zeta}_m]$, where m is the number of state equations, such that each set appears in a single state equation, then eqn. 1 results in a decoupled system of equations given by

$$y_j = \dot{x}_j = f_j(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\zeta}_j) \quad \forall j \in [1, m]. \quad (2)$$

This assumption is not overly restrictive, and aircraft parameter estimation problem can be framed in this form as shown in the next section. This results in considerable simplification of the parameter estimation problem without any loss of accuracy.

As the eqn 2 is decoupled in terms of $\boldsymbol{\zeta}_j$, they can be estimated individually, and the solution procedure will be identical for each equation. Hence, further description will be based on a single state equation, and the index j will be dropped, resulting in the form given below.

$$y = \dot{x} = f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\zeta}) \quad (3)$$

The popular classical methods of parameter estimation are the least squares, maximum likelihood estimation and Kalman filters[31]. Given the measured data² of the state and control variables, the least squares estimate of ζ for a general nonlinear dynamical system is found by

$$\hat{\zeta} = \arg \min_{\zeta} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(y'_i - f \left(x'_i, u'_i, \hat{\zeta} \right) \right)^2 \quad \forall i \in [1, N]. \quad (4)$$

However, this leads to a nonlinear optimization problem which may be multi-modal and may prove difficult to solve depending on the functional form of the right-hand side. Therefore, if the chosen parameter model is linear in ζ , then eqn 3 can be written as

$$y = \dot{x} = \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u})^T \zeta + k(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}). \quad (5)$$

With the assumption of linear dependence of parameter vector ζ over the system, eqn. 5 can be written in a matrix form as given below, with \mathbf{A} being the coefficient matrix and \mathbf{b} be a known vector.

$$\mathbf{A}\hat{\zeta} = \mathbf{b} \quad (6)$$

The eqn. 6 is a linear overdetermined system of equations to which the ordinary least squares method [31] gives the following closed-form solution.

$$\hat{\zeta} = (\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{b} \quad (7)$$

Readers can refer to [31] for a general overview of nonlinear least squares methods. Since the problem at hand can be solved efficiently in linear form, we have focused solely on this aspect.

The maximum likelihood estimation finds parameters that maximize the likelihood function

$$f_{likelihood} = \prod_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(y'_i - f(x'_i, u'_i, \zeta))^2}{2\sigma^2}}, \quad (8)$$

where σ is the standard deviation. The likelihood function computes the product of probability at each data point for given values of ζ , as each point is statistically independent. Maximizing the function increases the overall probability of estimated parameters in satisfying the governing equation at all data points.

To convert the problem to the standard minimization form and to improve the conditioning of the optimization network, most algorithms minimize the log-likelihood function

$$f_{obj} = -\log_{10} \left(\prod_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(y'_i - f(x'_i, u'_i, \zeta))^2}{2\sigma^2}} \right). \quad (9)$$

The Kalman filter estimates system parameters by exploiting the time evolution of the underlying dynamics. For nonlinear dynamical systems, the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) addresses nonlinearity through a piecewise linearization approach. In this formulation, the measurement data for x are assumed to be available, such that the governing equations take the below form.

$$\dot{x} = f(x, u, \zeta) \quad (10)$$

$$x' = g(x, u, \zeta) \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{\zeta} = 0 \quad (12)$$

Further details on the Kalman filter and its variants are available in the literature [8], [28], [31].

This completes our introduction to the parameter estimation, and the next section introduces PINNs.

²The variables with ' are measured values, whereas $\hat{\cdot}$ represents estimations.

Figure 1: Classical neural network

Figure 2: Data-less PINN

4 PINNs overview

In this section, we will present various neural network-based methods for the solution of forward and inverse problems for the dynamic system given by eqn. 3.

Figure 1 shows the classical neural network-based approach to the forward problem. This architecture has been widely used in non-scientific applications where the functional form of the relationship between the input and output is unknown; for example, image classification and natural language processing.

This architecture approximates the state \mathbf{x} as a function of time t and control variable \mathbf{u} . The model is trained by minimizing the loss function that compares the predicted and the measured data values. The standard choice of loss function is the mean-squared-error given as

$$L_D = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{x}_i - x'_i)^2. \quad (13)$$

It does not require the knowledge of the exact functional form of the system dynamics. The accuracy of predictions depends on the quality and quantity of the measurements. However, in scientific and engineering disciplines, it is expensive to obtain sufficient data through experiments and/or numerical simulations.

We note here that the classical methods for forward problems (for example Runge-Kutta integration methods) use a rigorously derived form of the basic physical laws to derive various levels of approximate functional relationships between input and output. This yields computationally efficient and accurate methods of predicting system behaviour. However, the classical methods cannot incorporate measurement data readily in their solution process.

In order to augment data with the underlying physics, Raissi, Perdikaris, and Karniadakis [39] demonstrated successful implementation and application of PINNs for solving forward problems. The Figure 2, shows the PINN architecture in its purest form without using state data. It should be noted here that this is not an autonomous system and so, the control history $\mathbf{u}(t)$ is to be provided as an input.

PINNs train a network that maps input to output in such a way that the physical laws (algebraic as well as differential equations) are satisfied at user-specified points inside the domain [27]. This is achieved by setting the loss function (L_{RES}) to be the mean squared error (MSE) of the residuals of the governing equations at specified internal points. Similarly, initial and boundary conditions (ICs & BCs) are imposed by augmenting the loss function with the MSE of the residuals at initial and boundary

Figure 3: Data-augmented PINN

Figure 4: PINN for parameter estimation

points.

$$L_{RES} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\dot{\hat{x}}_i - f(\hat{x}_i, \mathbf{u}'_i, \zeta) \right)^2 \quad (14)$$

$$L_{IC} = \frac{1}{N_{IC}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{IC}} (\hat{x}_{IC,i} - x'_{IC,i})^2 \quad (15)$$

$$L_{BC} = \frac{1}{N_{BC}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{BC}} (\hat{x}_{BC,i} - x'_{BC,i})^2 \quad (16)$$

All the neural network libraries use automatic differentiation[2] to compute the gradients of the loss function during back-propagation. The same automatic differentiation can be used to compute the derivatives of neural network output with respect to its input, such as the term $\dot{\hat{x}}_i$ in eqn. 14 in a relatively straightforward fashion. Combining eqns. 14 to 16 yields the physics loss function

$$L_P = L_{RES} + L_{IC} + L_{BC}. \quad (17)$$

For this approach (henceforth called the data-less approach) the control vector \mathbf{u} and time t are given as input to the model, and the predicted state variable $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ is fed to the physics loss function. The model is trained by minimizing L_P . Thus, the predicted state variables are expected to satisfy the underlying physics.

PINNs are known to suffer from high training cost. However, this can be improved by augmenting physics learning with available data. This leads to what are known as data-augmented PINNs for forward problems as illustrated in Figure 3.

This architecture is a hybrid between the classical neural network and the data-less PINN, as it learns from both data and physics. The model based on this architecture will be trained by minimizing the weighted sum of data loss L_D (eqn. 13) and physics loss L_P (eqn. 17) as

$$L = \omega L_D + (1 - \omega) L_P, \quad 0 \leq \omega \leq 1. \quad (18)$$

The advantage of the hybrid nature of data-augmented PINNs is that, as $\omega \rightarrow 0$, the model training will be based more on the physics than data, and vice versa. Thus, the value of ω can be determined via experimentation and the physical insight into the problem.

The data-augmented PINNs are enhanced to solve the inverse problem as shown in Figure 4. In the inverse problem, the parameters ζ defining system dynamics are unknown and are to be estimated using a set of measurement data $(t, \mathbf{u}', \mathbf{x}')$. This architecture has system parameters ζ as trainable variables to be estimated during the training process. Thus, an estimation for these parameters is obtained at the end of model training.

This dual use of data and physics leads to higher accuracy and less training cost as will be shown in the upcoming section. Also, it will be demonstrated that this leads to a more robust algorithm for parameter estimation given low-fidelity data. In the next section, we demonstrate the efficacy of this approach with a model problem.

5 Parameter estimation of Hansa aircraft

We have selected the sufficiently complex problem of parameter estimation of the longitudinal flight dynamics of Hansa aircraft [33] to demonstrate the capabilities of PINNs. The measurement data is

generated synthetically (as opposed to actual measurements) to investigate the accuracy of the proposed method and remove the effect of measurement noise on the prediction accuracy. The synthetic data was generated using the linear aerodynamic model for the Hansa aircraft reported by Rangaranjan and Vishwanathan [42] from the wind tunnel experiments.

Governing equations of the longitudinal flight dynamics were derived by applying Newton's laws of conservation of linear and angular momentum to the aircraft. The simulation parameters are listed in Table 1. The eqns. 19 to 22 give the longitudinal state equations in the wind axis system [31]. The implemented aerodynamic model is represented by eqns. 23 to 25 along with Table 2.

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = -\frac{\bar{q}S}{m}C_D + \frac{T}{m}\cos(\alpha) + g\sin(\alpha - \theta) \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = -\frac{\bar{q}S}{mV}C_L + q - \frac{T}{mV}\sin(\alpha) + \frac{g}{V}\cos(\alpha - \theta) \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{dq}{dt} = \frac{\bar{q}S\bar{c}}{I_{yy}}C_m \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{d\theta}{dt} = q \quad (22)$$

$$C_L = C_{L_0} + C_{L_\alpha}\alpha + C_{L_q}\frac{q\bar{c}}{2V} + C_{L_{\delta_e}}\delta_e \quad (23)$$

$$C_D = C_{D_0} + C_{D_\alpha}|\alpha| + C_{D_{\delta_e}}|\delta_e| \quad (24)$$

$$C_m = C_{m_0} + C_{m_\alpha}\alpha + C_{m_q}\frac{q\bar{c}}{2V} + C_{m_{\delta_e}}\delta_e \quad (25)$$

Here, $\bar{q} = \frac{1}{2}\rho V^2$ denotes the dynamic pressure, α is the angle of attack, q the pitch rate, V the freestream velocity, θ the pitch angle and δ_e the elevator deflection angle.

We note here that the eqns. 19 to 22 are decoupled with respect to the unknown aerodynamic coefficients. For example, C_{D_0} , C_{D_α} and $C_{D_{\delta_e}}$ appear only in eqn. 19. Hence, each equation can be written in the separated scalar form of eqn 5. This enables us to perform parameter estimation independently by considering each equation individually.

Table 1: Simulation parameters

Parameter	Value
Mean aerodynamic chord (\bar{c})	1.211 <i>m</i>
Wing span (<i>b</i>)	10.47 <i>m</i>
Aspect Ratio (<i>AR</i>)	8.8
Wing area (<i>S</i>)	12.47 <i>m</i> ²
Mass (<i>m</i>)	750.0 <i>kg</i>
Moment of inertia (I_{yy})	907.0 <i>kg/m</i> ²
Span efficiency factor (<i>e</i>)	0.8
Engine Thrust (<i>T</i>)	1136.0 <i>N</i>
Air density (ρ)	1.225 <i>kg/m</i> ³

Table 2: Aerodynamic derivatives obtained from wind tunnel experiments

Derivative	Value	Derivative	Value	Derivative	Value
C_{L_0}	0.354	C_{m_0}	0.052	C_{D_0}	0.036
C_{L_α}	4.972	C_{m_α}	-0.496	C_{D_α}	0.061
C_{L_q}	37.259	C_{m_q}	-11.790	$C_{D_{\delta_e}}$	0.026
$C_{L_{\delta_e}}$	0.265	$C_{m_{\delta_e}}$	-1.008		

Synthetic data was generated by integrating eqns. 19 to 25 from the initial state given in Table 3. A fully implicit fifth-order Runge-Kutta method of the Radau family[46], [55] and a custom elevator

Table 3: Initial values of state variables

State	Value
Velocity (V)	41.420 m/s
Angle of attack (α)	0.036 rad
Pitch rate (q)	0.038 rad/s
Pitch angle (θ)	0.150 rad

Figure 5: Elevator deflection profile (in radians) vs time

Figure 6: State variables data for given input elevator deflection profile

deflection control input δ_e (Figure 5) was used for the data generation with a time step of 0.02 seconds for the flight duration of 14.8 seconds. Thrust and mass of the aircraft were taken to be constant throughout the simulated flight time.

Thus, the synthetic flight data has 740 data points of four state variables, covering 14.8 seconds of flight time, for the given control inputs of δ_e and T .

5.1 Classical methods solution

The methods of ordinary Least Squares (LS), Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) and Extended Kalman Filters (EKF) were used to estimate the aerodynamic derivatives using synthetic data and aircraft system parameters.

In the least squares method, the linear aerodynamic model equations corresponding to each coefficient, C_D , C_L , and C_m , were substituted into their appropriate state equations. Then, they were rearranged into the matrix form

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{X}\hat{\zeta}. \quad (26)$$

For example, the matrix equation framed for the estimation of C_D coefficients with all the measured state and control³ variables will become

$$\begin{aligned} & \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{m}{\bar{q}S} \left(\frac{dV'}{dt} - \frac{T'}{m} \cos(\alpha') - \frac{g}{V'} \sin(\alpha' - \theta') \right) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \alpha' & \delta'_e \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_{D_0} \\ C_{D_\alpha} \\ C_{D_{\delta_e}} \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Then eqn. 7 gives the estimate for the aerodynamic derivatives.

In MLE, the aerodynamic model equation was substituted in the state equation and then taken in residual form to the log likelihood function eqn. 9. Taking the same C_D estimation as an example, the log likelihood function will be of the form

$$f_{obj} = -\log_{10} \left(\prod_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(\lambda)}{2\sigma^2}} \right), \quad (28)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda = \frac{dV'}{dt} \Big|_i - & \left(-\frac{\bar{q}_i S}{m} (C_{D_0} + C_{D_\alpha} \alpha'_i + C_{D_{\delta_e}} \delta'_{e,i}) \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{T'}{m} \cos \alpha'_i + g \sin (\alpha'_i - \theta'_i) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Minimization was performed using BFGS algorithm to yield MLE estimates of C_{D_0} , C_{D_α} and $C_{D_{\delta_e}}$.

The procedure for implementing the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) was adopted from the established benchmark studies in the literature[8], [28]. Using this framework, estimations of the aerodynamic model parameters were subsequently obtained.

The LS, MLE and EKF predictions were compared with the wind tunnel (WT) values and the estimations were tabulated in Table 4 (presented in the next section). It was found that the prediction error percentages, E_p ⁴ of the derivatives of coefficients C_L and C_D were of the order of 10^{-2} , whereas the same for C_m were relatively high, the highest being over 2% for C_{m_α} estimation. The next section outlines the estimation methodology of the same problem using PINNs.

6 PINN solution to the Hansa problem

The initial trial in solving the Hansa problem was with the Determinant PINN architecture[29] (see Figure 7). The network maps time t to the state variables. This network is trained on the data loss function for the state variables and physics loss function which gets the derivative information using automatic differentiation of the network. The aerodynamic derivatives are the trainable variables and are estimated during model training.

Next we tried the Modified Non-Determinant PINN architecture[29] (See Figure 8). In this architecture, the network maps α and δ_e to the drag coefficient C_D using physics loss function. The state variable derivative information is calculated using finite difference method. This network cannot estimate the aerodynamic derivatives but gives C_D as an explicit function of α and δ_e .

We found that the problem was solvable using both the PINN architectures, and the estimated results were sufficiently accurate. However, the Determinant PINN requires more computing resources as it predicts the already known state variables along with parameter estimation, and the Modified

³The variables with ' on it are measured values, whereas $\hat{\cdot}$ represents estimations.

⁴Error percentage for a general parameter ν is defined as, $E_p = \text{abs}(\hat{\nu} - \nu)/\nu \times 100$

Figure 7: Modified schematic of Determinant PINN[29] applied for C_D model coefficient estimation

Figure 8: Modified schematic of Modified Non-determinant PINN[29] applied for C_D model coefficient estimation

Non-determinant PINN requires the values of the state variable derivatives that are pre-computed using finite difference. The finite difference methods have limitations in approximating a derivative (truncation and subtractive cancellation errors) and using them on a low-fidelity data leads to inaccurate derivative computation.

It should be noted that the Determinant PINN architecture can only be trained on the data points where the measurements of the entire state vector are available. As the data and physics loss functions are evaluated at each training point simultaneously, the training dataset gets reduced to the measurement set where all the measurements are available. As will be shown in the results section, this is a big limiting factor. The Modified Non-Determinant PINNs are faster but introduce inaccuracies by the finite difference calculation of state variable derivatives. And it also has the same limiting factor as the Determinant PINNs.

The training data with low-fidelity (such as partly missing data, time offsets and sparsity) have to be preprocessed so as to have values for all state and control variables at sufficient number of timesteps for accurate estimation. This becomes a two-stage process (data preprocessing and then training) and it is suboptimal. Hence, to obviate the need for the finite difference calculation of state variable derivatives and to maintain the efficacy of the network and its robustness to low-fidelity data, a new architecture was developed. It is called the System Identification PINNs (SI-PINNs). The schematic diagram of SI-PINN for C_D estimation is given in Figure 9. The schematic will be similar for C_L and C_m estimations with appropriate equations and aerodynamic model variables plugged in.

Figure 9: Schematic of SI-PINN for drag coefficient estimation

SI-PINN architecture for C_D estimation is a modular network design consisting of two networks: dynamics network (green) and parameter network (blue). The dynamics network maps time to a single state variable and is trained with a data loss function (eqn. 29) using state measurements.

$$L_D = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(V_i' - \hat{V}_i \right)^2 \quad (29)$$

Conventional neural network-based system identification approaches [15], [37] typically employ a single network that directly estimates coefficients from data. This necessitates the use of high-fidelity structured datasets, wherein all state variables are available at each time instant. In contrast, the modular SI-PINN architecture enables the dynamics network to be trained independently using the available data. This flexibility allows the architecture to handle unstructured data effectively, constituting the key innovation that facilitates robustness to low-fidelity data.

After training, the dynamics network is used to compute accurate derivatives of the state variables using automatic differentiation. This derivative information is fed into the parameter network's loss function to calculate the physics loss.

The parameter network models the terms dependent on the parameters (to be estimated) in the governing equations. For example, parameter network can be seen as an approximation to $(\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u})^T \boldsymbol{\zeta})$ in eqn. 5. This corresponds to $(\bar{q}S/m)C_D$ term in eqn. 19. However, in aircraft system identification, it is easier to work with aerodynamic coefficients. Hence, the parameter network maps C_D to the states and control variables on which it depends. For example, under the chosen aerodynamic model (eqn. 24) C_D depends on α and δ_e .

The physics loss function based on the residual of the state equation that is sufficient to train this network is

$$L_{state} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{d\hat{V}}{dt} \Big|_i - \frac{\bar{q}_i S}{m} \hat{C}_{D_i} - \frac{T}{m} \cos(\alpha'_i) - g \sin(\alpha'_i - \theta'_i) \right)^2. \quad (30)$$

However, apart from the usual weights and biases, parameter network also has the aerodynamic model derivatives C_{D_0} , C_{D_α} and $C_{D_{\delta_e}}$ defined as the trainable variables. The values of these trainable variables were computed by minimizing an additional objective function that imposes the aerodynamic model equation with estimated \hat{C}_D as

$$L_{ADmodel} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\hat{C}_{D_i} - C_{D_0} - C_{D_\alpha} \alpha'_i - C_{D_{\delta_e}} \delta'_{e_i} \right)^2. \quad (31)$$

Thus, the parameter network is trained by minimizing the physics loss function L_P which is a weighted sum of eqns. 30 and 31 given as

$$L_P = \omega L_{state} + (1 - \omega) L_{ADmodel}. \quad (32)$$

It should be noted that eqn. 30 and eqn. 31 can be combined together, mathematically, to remove estimated \hat{C}_D to get a single loss function. However, this cannot be done as \hat{C}_D is the output from the network and the gradients of the output with respect to input are required for training. Therefore, both eqns. 30 and 31 are evaluated separately and the weight $\omega = 0.5$ is the natural choice.

This network provides the estimate of \hat{C}_D in two forms: non-functional form and functional form. Non-functional form is arrived by setting $\omega = 1$. This trains the network only on the physics loss from the state equation. It can then be provided as the trained neural network for the online control and guidance algorithms.

If a functional form is selected apriori, then the corresponding aerodynamic model derivatives are also output from the training process which can be achieved by setting $\omega = 0.5$. This may be more useful for studying the aerodynamic characteristics of the aircraft in the offline mode. It can also be used for online state estimation.

The underlying aerodynamic model can be modified to incorporate any additional physics, like unsteady effects such as aeroelasticity and stall. Thus, this network can be used to perform the system identification analysis for any aircraft without major change in the network architecture. Hence the name "System Identification" PINNs (SI-PINNs).

The extension of SI-PINN architecture and training mechanism to other aerodynamic coefficients (C_L and C_m) is straightforward, with the appropriate state and aerodynamic model equations and inputs plugged in it.

Figure 10: SI-PINN: C_D prediction

6.1 Data normalization and model architecture

In general, the numerical values of all state and control variables are in different orders of magnitude (for example, α in $\mathcal{O}(10^{-2})$ and V in $\mathcal{O}(10^1)$). Training with such numerical values would bring down the significance of low order variables over higher-order ones by the network. Thus, all the values of variables are scaled to the same order, and in the deep learning community, the values are generally normalized to $\mathcal{O}(1)$. This is because most of the popular activation functions in the deep learning community are bounded to the range $[0, 1]$.

In this work, the data was normalized to the range $[0.05, 0.95]$ instead of $[0, 1]$ in order not to saturate the neurons in the network [41]. As discussed in previous sections, the governing equations are decoupled in the inverse problem definition; hence three SI-PINNs were developed, one for each of the three state equations (eqns. 19 to 21) with appropriate aerodynamic model equations substituted in them.

An ideal network configuration achieves a balance of low training cost, reduced evaluation time, and high accuracy. With these criteria in mind, hyperparameter tuning was performed, and a configuration consisting of five hidden layers with 15 neurons in each layer for both the dynamic and parameter networks was identified as providing an optimal trade-off between training efficiency and estimation accuracy. Hyperbolic tan activation function was used in all the layers of both the networks. We used the mean squared error ⁵ as the loss function for all the networks.

6.2 SI-PINNs estimation results

We trained three separate SI-PINNs, for lift, drag, and pitching moment coefficients using the synthetic data, and obtained the time series estimation of C_D , C_m and C_L values along with the residuals of the governing equations. They are shown in Figures 10 to 15. We found that the estimations of C_m and C_L coefficients were more accurate than C_D estimation despite having the same network configuration. This is because the thrust term in the right-hand side of eqn. 19 is significantly larger than the drag term; thus the network faced lack of training boost from the physics for this coefficient.

It should be noted that the residuals of all state and aerodynamic model equations are of the order of 10^{-4} , indicating that the network estimations closely adhere to the governing physical laws.

Table 4 displays the comparison between the SI-PINNs estimated values of the aerodynamic derivatives, the benchmark wind tunnel (WT) values, least squares (LS), maximum likelihood estimations (MLE), and the Extended Kalman Filters (EKF). The SI-PINNs were observed to perform on par with classical methods. Across all four approaches, the maximum estimation error was slightly above 2% for $C_{L_{\delta_a}}$.

The SI-PINNs demonstrated comparable performance to the classical methods when applied to high-fidelity data. To further assess the generalization capability of the SI-PINN framework, a cross-validation was conducted using a second dataset, as detailed in the following section.

⁵Mean squared error of a general quantity ν (V , for example) is defined as $\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\nu_i - \hat{\nu}_i)^2$, where ν_i and $\hat{\nu}_i$ are the i^{th} true value and the predicted value of the quantity

Figure 11: SI-PINN: V equation and C_D model equation residuals

Figure 12: SI-PINN: C_m prediction

Figure 13: SI-PINN: q equation and C_m model equation residuals

Figure 14: SI-PINN: C_L prediction

Figure 15: SI-PINN: α equation and C_L model equation residuals

Table 4: SI-PINNs estimation compared with LS, MLE, EKF and WT values

Coefficients	WT	SI-PINN		LS		MLE		EKF	
		Value	E_p	Value	E_p	Value	E_p	Value	E_p
C_{L_0}	0.365	0.3639	0.301	0.3651	0.054	0.3651	0.0276	0.3649	0.2681
C_{L_α}	4.972	4.9790	0.140	4.9712	0.016	4.9710	0.0198	4.9701	0.0380
C_{L_q}	37.259	37.4781	0.588	37.2921	0.088	37.3908	0.0855	37.4268	0.4504
$C_{L_{\delta_e}}$	0.265	0.2722	2.716	0.2583	2.528	0.2583	2.5248	0.2588	2.3343
C_{m_0}	0.050	0.0498	0.384	0.0499	0.192	0.0499	0.1104	0.0483	3.2520
C_{m_α}	-0.496	-0.4880	1.612	-0.4890	1.411	-0.4896	2.0764	-0.4740	4.4318
C_{m_q}	-11.310	-11.2741	0.220	-11.2811	0.165	-11.2816	0.2510	-10.9009	3.6165
$C_{m_{\delta_e}}$	-1.008	-1.0056	0.238	-1.0065	0.148	-1.0066	0.1368	-0.9748	3.2879
C_{D_0}	0.036	0.0360	0.136	0.0360	0.050	0.0360	0.0433	0.0359	0.1055
C_{D_α}	0.041	0.0405	1.007	0.0408	0.481	0.0408	0.4533	0.0408	0.4829
$C_{D_{\delta_e}}$	0.026	0.0258	0.769	0.0257	0.961	0.0257	0.8500	0.0258	0.7307

7 Numerical experiments with Hansa problem

In the practical experiments that are performed for the flight data generation, numerous problems will be faced in obtaining a valid dataset for parameter estimation. Here, we took a set of major difficulties faced in the data generation and we artificially imposed them on the synthetic data. The performance of SI-PINNs was demonstrated by training and evaluating them with these datasets.

Four numerical experiments that vary in training data quality and quantity were framed for testing SI-PINNs. As the neural networks were already shown to be robust to noises in the training data [38], noise handling was not included to be one among these experiments.

The same experiments were also performed using the least squares (LS) method for comparison. In contrast, MLE and the EKF rely heavily on model fidelity and the data sampling interval Δt . Their performance is being constrained by numerical integration of state equations when applied to sparse or truncated datasets that are encountered in these experiments. Consequently, these methods were excluded from the comparison to ensure fairness.

We chose SI-PINN network for C_D estimation for all the experiments.

7.1 Performance with sparse data

In the physical experiments, there are numerous sources of data, such as sensors that are deployed to extract the data from the wind tunnel test sections and test models. Occasionally, the data obtained could be faulty and only sparse amount of it can be usable for parameter estimation. This experiment simulates such a scenario by downsampling the original data successively.

The dataset contains a total of 740 points of state and control variable values spanning in time $t \in [0, 14.8]$ seconds. In this experiment, successively we drop the alternate data points to increase the Δt between data points (still maintaining $t \in [0, 14.8]$) used for parameter estimation. The training data is collected at equidistant intervals such that each set contains data points that are twice separated in time than the previous one, covering the entire domain. The SI-PINNs were trained on these datasets,

and the estimated C_D derivative values were compared against the least squares estimations, as given in Tables 5 to 7 and in Figure 16.

Table 5: C_{D_0} estimation using sparse data:
actual value $C_{D_0} = 0.036$

Δt	Data points	SI-PINN		LS	
		Value	E_p	Value	E_p
0.02	740	0.03604	0.136	0.03601	0.05
0.04	370	0.03606	0.168	0.03606	0.186
0.08	185	0.03600	0.002	0.03626	0.741
0.16	93	0.03603	0.098	0.03706	2.953
0.32	47	0.03588	0.315	0.04016	11.577

Table 6: C_{D_α} estimation using sparse data:
actual value $C_{D_\alpha} = 0.041$

Δt	Data points	SI-PINN		LS	
		Value	E_p	Value	E_p
0.02	740	0.04058	1.007	0.04080	0.048
0.04	370	0.04034	1.596	0.04026	1.798
0.08	185	0.04014	2.089	0.03805	7.184
0.16	93	0.04074	0.632	0.02925	28.656
0.32	47	0.04240	3.419	-0.00515	112.582

Table 7: $C_{D_{\delta_e}}$ estimation using sparse data:
actual value $C_{D_{\delta_e}} = 0.026$

Δt	Data points	SI-PINN		LS	
		Value	E_p	Value	E_p
0.02	740	0.02583	0.653	0.02575	0.961
0.04	370	0.02539	2.309	0.02508	3.506
0.08	185	0.02522	2.972	0.02235	14.002
0.16	93	0.02588	0.428	0.01148	55.808
0.32	47	0.02801	7.742	-0.03105	219.445

Figure 16: Prediction E_p of C_D derivatives with sparse data

It can be seen that SI-PINN did better than least squares in all derivatives. Error in the least squares rises more rapidly than SI-PINNs as the data becomes sparse. SI-PINNs are able to achieve good estimation accuracy even for sparse data with the help of physics information.

However, E_p fluctuations of SI-PINN in low ranges were observed near the sparse data range due to the stochastic nature of the optimization algorithm. These fluctuations could be eliminated by ensemble averaging, i.e. by performing multiple SI-PINN estimations with different initial conditions and taking an average estimation.

This difference in the performance can be attributed to the gradient calculation step on eqn. 19. Least squares use finite differences, which would lead to large errors with large step sizes for sparse data. Whereas in SI-PINN, automatic differentiation based gradient calculation on eqn. 19 leads to lower error with sparse data, as the model fits a continuous and differentiable function over the sparse data that yields better gradient values.

7.2 Performance with data having multiple sampling frequency

Another interesting scenario of practical importance is the disparity in the sampling frequency of sensors used for measurements. This leads to differences in the number of data points available for each variable over a given period of time. Here, the data sampling frequency of each sensor may not be the same, which leads to differences in the number of data points available for each variable recorded over a given time. This leads to the handling of unstructured data⁶. Thus, in this experiment, the performance of SI-PINNs in handling the data with multiple sampling frequencies is demonstrated.

For conducting this experiment, 93 equispaced points of V data was taken in the $t \in [0, 14.8]$ domain, indicating a low sampling frequency of 6.5 Hz. The other state and control variables were collected with 185 equispaced points which is approximately twice the number of V data points and corresponds to a frequency of 12.5 Hz. We chose these specific sampling frequencies in order to amplify the differences in estimations of SI-PINNs and least squares. The SI-PINN was trained using this data and the C_D derivatives were estimated.

The same experiment was performed using least squares for comparison. However, least squares requires all the data to be sampled at the same frequency (structured data). Hence, the only option for least squares in this experiment was to use the data with the lowest sampling frequency of 6.5 Hz without performing data pre-processing. The estimated C_D derivatives of both SI-PINNs and least squares are given in Table 8.

Table 8: Estimated C_D model coefficients using data with multiple sampling frequency

Derivative	WT	SI-PINN		LS	
		Value	E_p	Value	E_p
C_{D_0}	0.036	0.03608	0.245	0.03706	2.953
C_{D_α}	0.041	0.04015	2.071	0.02925	28.652
$C_{D_{\delta_e}}$	0.026	0.02506	3.612	0.01148	55.804

As the data sampling frequency reduced, the prediction accuracy of least squares declined due to the availability of less data points, as demonstrated in the previous experiment. The maximum error percentage E_p occurring for $C_{D_{\delta_e}}$ estimation was around 56% for least squares and around 4% for SI-PINNs. Table 8 shows that the SI-PINNs' estimations are better than the least squares, as the neural networks can learn functions with unstructured data. On the other hand, the least squares method requires data pre-processing for obtaining the structured data for the estimation.

7.3 Performance with data having time offset

In general, a physical experiment will have as many sensors as the state variables to be measured. Thus, a synchronized start of recording data by all the sensors cannot be assured and results in time offsets. In this experiment, the SI-PINNs were tested with the data that have the same sampling frequency but with a time offset in recording, that is, one variable is recorded at times starting from 0, $2\Delta t$, $4\Delta t$ etc. while the other variables are recorded at times starting from Δt , $3\Delta t$, $5\Delta t$ etc. where $2\Delta t$ is the recording time step.

⁶Structured data contains all variable values at each time step, while unstructured data may have individual variable values recorded at different time steps.

Table 9: SI-PINN estimated C_D model coefficient values for exp. with sparse data having time-offset

Derivative	WT	SI-PINN	E_p
C_{D_0}	0.036	0.03607	0.209
C_{D_α}	0.041	0.04018	1.971
$C_{D_{\delta_e}}$	0.026	0.02509	3.472

Table 10: Estimation of C_D model coefficients with truncated data

Derivative	WT	SI-PINN		LS	
		Value	E_p	Value	E_p
C_{D_0}	0.036	0.03596	0.098	0.03629	0.827
C_{D_α}	0.041	0.04199	2.410	0.03774	7.943
$C_{D_{\delta_e}}$	0.026	0.02527	2.792	0.02214	14.821

To generate the data, a equispaced 370 data points were taken in the same $t \in [0, 14.8]$ domain. The velocity data points were taken at times starting from 0.04 s, 0.12 s etc. while other state variables are recorded at 0, 0.08s etc, giving a total of 185 training data points.

The SI-PINN was trained with this data, and the estimates on C_D model coefficients were given in Table 9. However, least squares cannot be used with this dataset without pre-processing as there were time-wise unsynchronized values. The maximum error percentage E_p of SI-PINNs estimations occurring in $C_{D_{\delta_e}}$ was over 3.5%. Hence, SI-PINNs was able to estimate the C_D derivatives with appreciable accuracy without the need for data preprocessing.

7.4 Performance with truncated data

Measurement sensors can malfunction or give noisy output intermittently during the experiments. This may lead to missing data segments in one or more variables. For example, velocity measurement may fail in a segment (Figure 17) while we might have complete measurement data for all other variables. This scenario of truncated data for one of the state variables is simulated in this experiment.

In general, the truncated data is preprocessed by either interpolating to construct missing data (for input data) or treating the missing data as unknown parameters (for output data)[49]. Here, we demonstrate that the SI-PINNs achieve good estimation accuracy without need for such data preprocessing.

In this numerical experiment, a dataset spanning 14.8 seconds with 370 equispaced points was taken. In V data, three segments of length 1 second each were cut to simulate the truncated data, while the other variables were taken in full. The location of truncation was manually chosen to have a linear region, a slightly non-linear and a complete non-linear region to induce complexity. Then, this data was used to estimate the C_D profile, and its derivatives using SI-PINNs. Least squares (LS) estimation was also obtained with this dataset for comparison.

The data was normalized and directly used to train the SI-PINNs. However, data pre-processing was needed for the least squares. The data corresponding three missing segments in V were removed from the other variables, and the truncated data was used for the least squares estimation. The estimated results of both least squares and SI-PINN are presented in Table 10 and Figure 17.

SI-PINNs' ability to fill the truncated segments can be clearly observed in Figure 17. The thin yellow line in Figure 17 represents the prediction of V from the dynamics network of SI-PINN. The red \circ markers were the data points used for training the SI-PINNs and for the least squares estimation. The thick blue line is the predictions in SI-PINN after training and the yellow line represents the actual full data. However, the yellow line completely coincides with the thick blue line, indicating good estimation on missing data. The C_D derivatives estimation of SI-PINNs is also more accurate than the least squares.

It can be clearly seen that the SI-PINNs are good at reconstructing the truncated data. However, it should be noted that the region of data truncation play an important role in the profile reconstruction. If the data was missed in areas of steep changes, then the estimation accuracy will be compromised. The pre-processing methods like interpolation, curve fit, and even neural networks could not guarantee an estimate that matches with full data.

The least squares method uses finite differences over the interpolated data for the gradient computation, which adds more error to the estimation. However, SI-PINNs with its machine accurate automatic

Figure 17: SI-PINN predicted velocity profile compared to actual and truncated data

differentiation would perform better than least squares in this circumstance as well. Thus, SI-PINNs can handle truncated data for estimation without the need for pre-processing and yield sufficiently accurate results. While the data pre-processing is must for the least squares method.

Results from all four numerical experiments show that the SI-PINNs have notably exceeded least squares in prediction accuracy when using low-fidelity data without the need for pre-processing⁷.

In the next section we extend the SI-PINNs architecture to handle low-fidelity data for all the state and control variables simultaneously.

8 Robust SI-PINNs (RSI-PINNs)

The numerical experiments performed in the previous section assumed that low-fidelity data was used solely for the dynamics network, with the parameter network receiving structured data. However, in real-world scenarios, low-fidelity data can pertain to any state and control variable. Therefore, the SI-PINNs architecture needs to be robust enough to accommodate low-fidelity data across all variables. Hence, the name *Robust SI-PINNs* (RSI-PINNs) for the enhanced architecture. The schematic of RSI-PINN for C_D estimation is given in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Schematic of the Robust SI-PINN for C_D estimation

The RSI-PINNs architecture is a natural extension of the SI-PINNs' modular network design, having

⁷Here, data pre-processing refers to the process of enhancing data fidelity rather than normalizing the data for the neural network training

individual dynamics networks dedicated to each state and control variable. These dynamics networks can independently handle low-fidelity data for each state and control variable, removing the need for coherence among sensor operations during data recording. These dynamics networks are trained individually using their respective data.

Once these dynamics networks are trained, they are linked to the parameter network and supplied with a common input dataset t . The parameter network is then trained to estimate the required aerodynamic coefficient (\hat{C}_D for example) using physics-based loss constraints.

The derivatives of the state variables used in the loss function can be obtained through automatic differentiation of the dynamics networks. This approach is similar to SI-PINN, but RSI-PINN allows for the simultaneous computation of derivatives for all state variables. The parameter network also has a set of trainable variables that estimates the values of aerodynamic model derivatives. Hence, the same redundancy in estimation is preserved in RSI-PINNs as well.

The primary aim of the RSI-PINN architecture is to effectively handle low-fidelity data across all state and control variables. To showcase this capability, an experiment was conducted with truncated data, and the performance was compared with the same network trained over full data. This test case is considered to be one of the most challenging scenarios described in the previous section.

The experiment was conducted for C_D estimation. Three non-overlapping one-second segments were omitted from the variables V , α , θ and δ_e for generating training data. The location of the data omission is selected randomly, which significantly increases the complexity of the problem.

The RSI-PINN dynamics networks are trained with this truncated data, and Figure 19 shows the estimated complete profiles of state and control variables along with full profile and the truncated training data. It can be seen that the V and θ are approximated by the network well in the segments with missing data, whereas α and δ_e didn't. This is because of the steep data variation in those missing segments.

Then the parameter network is trained with physics-based constraints using this estimated state and control variable data. Figure 20 shows the comparison between C_D profiles that are predicted using full and truncated data, with the actual profile.

RSI-PINN has estimated the C_D profile with maximum error percentage of the order of 10^{-2} with the full data, demonstrating the effectiveness of the method. However, with the truncated data, the maximum error percentage of C_D estimation is just over 1.5%. This was obtained without data pre-processing for the missing segments.

Figure 19: State and control profiles estimated by RSI-PINN with missing data

The aerodynamic model derivatives estimated with both full and truncated data are presented in Table 11. These estimations were done in one-shot prediction without any data preprocessing. On the other hand, the least squares method, if implemented, cannot handle this faulty data without preprocessing, and there is no guarantee that the interpolation of the missing gaps will match the full data.

Figure 20: C_D estimation of RSI-PINNs with full and missing dataset, and the corresponding error percentage profiles

Table 11: RSI-PINN estimations of C_D model coefficients with full and missing data

Derivative	WT	Full data		Missing data	
		Value	E_p	Value	E_p
C_{D_0}	0.036	0.03603	0.083	0.03547	1.450
C_{D_α}	0.041	0.04073	0.658	0.04515	10.139
$C_{D_{\delta_e}}$	0.026	0.02586	0.538	0.02475	4.783

Our experiments with the truncated data show that the prediction accuracy of the aerodynamic derivatives greatly depends on the location of the missing segments. For example, in the present diabolical case, the estimates are especially bad because of the missing data in the areas of steep changes, mainly in α and δ_e variables (Figure 19).

In the present work, RSI-PINN was demonstrated for C_D estimation only. However, the architecture of RSI-PINN is so general that it enables the simultaneous estimation of all three aerodynamic coefficients, C_D , C_L and C_m by plugging in the appropriate governing equations in the loss function.

The RSI-PINNs demonstrated their capability to estimate quantities effectively, even with the low-fidelity data used for training. Therefore, it can be concluded that employing PINNs can reduce experimental costs by allowing the use of lower-fidelity equipment for data recording.

Another advantage of RSI-PINNs is that the derivatives of all supplied state variables can be computed simultaneously. This allows the network to be used for estimating all three aerodynamic coefficients (C_L , C_m and C_D) simultaneously by plugging in appropriate state and aerodynamic model equations in the loss functions. Hence, one network can estimate all the coefficients even with low-fidelity data.

9 Conclusion

In this study, we demonstrated offline parameter estimation of the longitudinal flight dynamics of the Hansa aircraft using Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs). A novel architecture, termed System Identification PINNs (SI-PINNs), was proposed to address the limitations of existing approaches in handling low-fidelity flight data.

The SI-PINN architecture is a modular network design consisting of a dynamics network and a parameter network. The dynamics network was trained independently using the available data from a single state. This flexibility allows the architecture to handle unstructured data effectively, constituting

the key innovation that facilitates robustness to low-fidelity data. The dynamics network was then differentiated to obtain state derivatives that will be used in the physics loss function of the parameter network.

The parameter network captures the aerodynamic model through training with a physics-informed loss function. The aerodynamic derivatives are incorporated as trainable variables into the parameter network. The performance of SI-PINNs was benchmarked against classical approaches such as least-squares, maximum-likelihood estimation, and Kalman filtering for the high-fidelity datasets.

A series of numerical experiments, reflecting practical data-generation challenges, were conducted to evaluate the performance of SI-PINNs under low-fidelity data conditions. Classical methods such as least squares require data preprocessing and manual fine-tuning when applied to low-fidelity data. In contrast, SI-PINNs demonstrate improved estimation performance compared to least squares without requiring preprocessing.

To handle low-fidelity data across multiple states and control variables, the SI-PINN architecture was extended to Robust SI-PINNs (RSI-PINNs). The RSI-PINN architecture employs dedicated dynamics networks for each state and control variable, enabling it to handle low-fidelity data across all states and controls while maintaining consistent estimation accuracy.

Classical estimation methods require extensive model structure definition and manual data preprocessing. In contrast, this proof-of-concept aircraft system identification study demonstrates that modern machine learning frameworks can operate directly on low-fidelity raw measurement data. This capability reduces overall development effort and makes them a practical alternative for aircraft system identification.

It should be noted that these methods require longer training times than classical approaches and are therefore slower for linear systems. For nonlinear system identification problems where the classical iterative optimization methods were used, the computational effort of machine learning-based methods becomes comparable to that of the classical methods.

Future work will focus on extending the approach to full aircraft dynamics, evaluating its effectiveness for nonlinear aerodynamic models, and improving computational speed and efficiency to enable online parameter estimation.

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